

Contribution of Indian Tribals to Modern Civilization

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ABSTRACT

According to one estimate there are 427 Scheduled Tribe communities in India with a population of 67,758,380 as per 1991 census. The prerogative for their development in modern India ensues from Article 46 of the Constitution of India, which reads thus: "The State shall promote with special care the educational and economic interests of the weaker sections of the people, and, in particular, of the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, and shall protect them from social justice and all forms of exploitation". The word 'tribe' has not been defined anywhere in the Constitution of India. But it states in Article 342 that the Scheduled Tribes are tribes or the tribal communities or parts of groups within tribes or tribal communities which the President may specify from time to time by public notification. As these communities are presumed to constitute the oldest ethnological segment of the Indian society, the term "Adivasi (Adi' means oldest and 'vasi' means inhabitant) is commonly used to designate them. India, a Secular, Democratic and Socialistic Republic has been pursuing a policy of cultural pluralism ever since it became independent. Pandit. Jawaharlal Nehru, the first Prime Minister of India, had declared that: "We should help the tribal people to develop along the lines of their own tradition and genius, teaching them not to despise their past, but to build upon it" (quoted in Elwin, 1963: 5)

Keywords: Secular, Democratic, Republic, Tribe communities, Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes, and Adivasi.

Introduction

The tribals are the aborigines and the only surviving remnants of the primitive human societies of India. They still love to live in their natural abodes, comprising the hills and forests, the river banks and lake shores and practise their traditional culture, rituals and customs, dance and music, arts and crafts, and traditional system of medicine for health care within their self-sustained forest ecosystem. Their traditional beliefs and practices have helped them in the preservation of their age old culture and with it the conservation of the physical, biological and ecological legacies which have come to modern India as a great heritage from these ancient people. Unfortunately with the onslaught of industrialization, urbanization and modernization in the tribal zones of India, the age-old tradition and culture of these primitive human societies with their entire social, cultural and ecological legacies are threatened with extinction.

Origin of Tribals

The inhabitants of the hills in this region are Malaiyalis. 'Malaiyali' means 'inhabitants of the hills'. In Tamil, malai means hill or mountain, and yali means ruler or inhabitant. There are three different theories about their origin.' The first one claims that they were migrants from the North Indian hills during the Aryan invasion, who had settled down in the uninhabited hills of Tamil Nadu. According to Kanakasabhai (1979), these people, natives of a mountainous region of north of Bengal, have chosen and occupied the hilly tracts such as the Kolli hills (in Salem district), the Western Ghats and the Nilgiris"

The second theory argues that Malaiyalis were native Tamils who were there right from the ancient Sangam period (3 ac to an 3)," It is being cited that the word Malaur found in the Sangam classics denotes them. This theory claims that in the ancient Tamil country there existed three distinctive Tamil-speaking people, namely Aborigines, Dravidian Tamils and Aryan migrants The third theory claims that they were migrants of recent times. According to the manuals, gazetteers and government reports, they were Tamil-speaking people who had migrated from the plains in comparatively recent times. They are, however, distinct from those in the plains and quite different from the Malayalam-speaking people of Kerala, although the name connotes both." They are neither a carnivorous ethnic group like some tribes in the Nilgiris, where there is discrimination among the hill inhabitants," nor are

they treated as untouchables like the scheduled castes. Although there is evidence in the Sangam literature to prove that the tribals had lived in the mountains of Tamil Nadu since the ancient times, details about their socio-economic, political, administrative and judicial institutions were not available until the close of the 18th century or the advent of the British. The colonial records, while maintaining that the tribals were migrants from the plains between the 14th and 16th centuries, also admit the possibility of the hills being inhabited prior to this exodus. Malayalis of South Arcot, North Arcot, Salem, Dharmapuri and Tiruchirappalli districts were emigrants from Kancheepuram (Chengalpattu district) during the 16th century. However, there are different versions about their migration."

The characteristic features of the Tamil-speaking Malaiyali tribes are different from the Todas, who still follow a pastoral economy and have a different name in each of the hill groups. In the Baramahal Records, they are known as 'Malaiyandi Vellallu. In general, they are called Mala Vellalar, Kongu Vellalar, Kanchimandalathar, Malaikkaran, Malai Kavundan, Mala Nayakkan, Malayala, Malaiyalan, Karaikat Vellalas, Karala Vellalas, Kanchimandala Vellalas and Karalan." All have Kavundan' as the second name, which is universally used to hail their genealogy. Despite being called differently in different hills, they are not distinct from each other apparently, they are ordinary Tamils, who, after migrating to the hill, have developed some local customs unique to them. People of the Vellala community in the plains have also settled in the hills. Before the arrival of the plains people, tribal communities such as Vedan and Beder had lived in the different hills of this region." Francis (1906) says, The hills were inhabited by vedans... the malayalis killed the men, and wedded the women, and at marriages a gun is still fired in the air to represent the death of the vedan husband. According to Ehrenfels, They adopt new ideas from neighbours or invaders without realizing that by so doing their former social system gets disintegrated. The present day tribals are neither purely hill inhabitants nor migrants from the plains but remain a mixture of both the streams with their own new system, developed in the course of time. However, they are not ethnically distinctive groups.

The Tribes of India

According to racial anthropologists, about six different races have migrated to India from outside from time to time and have taken root here. These are Negrito, the Proto-Australoid, the Mongoloid, the Mediterranean, the Western Brachycephals and the Nordic.

The dominant physical type in India are Proto-Australoid, the Negrito and the Mongoloid. The Constitution of India provides for special care to the tribals under the provisions of Article 46 and constitutionally they have been classified as the "Scheduled Tribes". There are about 212 Scheduled Tribes in India constituting approximately 7.7% of India's total population. Growth of tribal population is very slow. According to the census reports of India they were only 39 million in 1971 and in 1981 they became 52 millions. They only added another 10 million by 1991. In spite of the steady growth in the rate of their population some of the tribes are facing the danger of extinction.

Considering their historical, ethnical and socio-cultural relations the tribal landscape in various regions of India is classified into seven geographical zones:

1. The North-East India comprising the hills of Assam, Arunachal Pradesh, Nagaland, Manipur, Mizoram and Meghalaya. This is represented by the tribes Garo, Mikir, Naga, Abor, Bodo, Angami and Khasi. They live in the mountain valleys and are at a higher plane of development and not quite primitive. Physically they are Mongoloid with a light skin and muscular body.
2. The Sub-Himalayan region of North and North-West India comprising Uttar Pradesh and Himachal Pradesh. The representing tribes are Tharus, Gujar, Lodhs, Majhi, Nats, Gonds and Gaddis. They live in the foothills of Himalayas in the Kumaon region and have Mongoloid features.
3. The Eastern India comprising West Bengal, Bihar and Orissa. The important tribes living in this zone are Oraon, Rabha, Saora, Asurs, Santhals, Ho and Munda. They are black skinned and thin built. They use bow and arrow for hunting and for self-defence even today.
4. The Central India comprising Madhya Pradesh and represented by the Gonds, Maria, Koya and Kurku tribes. They are primitive, dark skinned people with a heavy nose and thick lips. Hill Marias are tall and handsome.
5. The Western India comprising the States of Rajasthan, Gujarat and Maharashtra. This is mostly represented by the Bhils which are the third largest tribe in India. Other tribes are Grassias the Rajput Grassias, Dhankas, Gamits etc. They are at a higher plane of development and have undergone the largest amount of acculturation from their Hindu

neighbours and have borrowed their customs and practices liberally. Some of them are nomadic and always carry arms with them.

6. The South-India comprising Tamil Nadu, Kerala, Karnataka and Andhra Pradesh. The important tribes are Toda, Kota, Badaga etc. They live under primitive conditions and are mostly located in the Nilgiri hills of South India.

7. The Indian islands comprising the Andaman and the Nicobar Islands. Onges and Jarawa are the important tribes of this region. Ethnologically Negrite, they still live in a Stone-Age culture. They live practically naked and are versatile users of bow and arrows. They are mostly hunters and agriculture is still not popular. The Jarwas are a vanishing tribe. They were about 200 in 1911 and now only 31 (Hindustan Times, 6 Nov. 1992).

Tribal population

There is no authentic account of the size of the tribal population until 1792. Only in 1793 were population statistics collected for the plains as well as the hill areas. But the reliability of the data can be questioned, because the Kalrayan hills did not come under direct colonial rule till then as it continued to be an independent region. The total population that is it was merely a supposition. The hills, which yielded revenue, were supposed to be inhabited." One of the major drawbacks of these estimates was that the rates of assessment were not identical among different hills and also within the same hill, as different rates were adopted for assessment. For instance, in Jawadhi hills, 125 rates had prevailed - 88 different rates for ploughs and 37 for hoes. Hence, the population data was nothing but an apparently crude estimation. It cannot be taken as a realistic count during the pre-colonial and early colonial rule in Salem and Baramahal region.

In 1793, there were 25 taluks in Salem and Baramahal. The hills in only 12 of them were occupied-five taluks, three from the southern division and two from the northern division, had a population of more than 1,000 people. Of the remaining, five had an insignificant population density, that is 1 per cent each of the southern and central divisions and 3 per cent of the northern division. The hills in the two remaining taluks had between 200 and 1,000 persons. The total population of Salem and Baramahal region in 1793 was about 600,000, of whom 27,713 (4.62 per cent) lived in the hills. The population density in the hills was lower than that of the plains. There were 3,159 people per square mile in the plains

against 174 in the hills. which also varied from 3 to 88 people. This shows that a large extent of land was left unoccupied at the time of colonial intervention, with the tribals having at their disposal vast tracts of forest lands.

Tribals and the forest: A symbiotic relationship for co-existence

Tribals are synonymous with the forests since their very inception on this earth and that is why they are also called vanyajati-the caste of the forest. They are an integral part of the forest ecosystem and like the other components of the terrestrial ecosystem they have been playing a significant role in the operation of the forest ecosystem and in the maintenance of the ecological balance in the area. The tribals have a symbiotic relationship with the forests, They derive their basic needs of survival from their host

i.e food (leaves, fruits, nuts, underground plant parts etc.) for themselves; fodder for their livestock; fuel for cooking. fibres for clothing, timbers, ropes, barks, wood, bamboos, and grasses for housing and farming, herbal medicines for health, and economic goods like gums, resins, waxes, honey, silkworm cocoons and several other valuable forest produce. In turn they protect the forest and also enrich its fertility through their various cultural activities, beliefs and practices. The forests not only give livelihood to the tribals but they also provide them with a social bonding and a culture reminiscent of their ancestors. The tribal culture is inexorably woven around the forest. The tribal women regard forest as their Maika (father's home) and the trees are held sacred. Even if a tribal cuts a tree or clears some patch of forest for making a home and farm they take the vow of planting several times more trees than those removed (Sinha 1991).

The ecological legacy: Preservation of biodiversity

'Animism' and 'naturalism' are part of the cultural life, beliefs and practices of the tribals in India. Plants, animals, trees, rivers, ponds, lakes, hills, stones and mountains are all considered sacred 'Nature worship' is a form of belief and all nature's creation has to be protected. The faith of these aboriginal people in Nature's creation has greatly helped in the preservation and protection of many natural ecosystems in India. Such tribal beliefs have survived several 'virgin forests in India in its pristine glory which have been termed as the Sacred groves (Forests of God) Sacred groves are patches of forest or a part of the large forest left untouched by the local inhabitants and all interferences into it are a taboo. It is

usually dedicated to a diety or a 'mother goddess' who is supposed to protect and preside over the grove and the intruders will be punished. It is believed that such a virgin forest dates back to several thousand years when human society in India was in its primitive state ie in the hunting-gathering stage. Hence it is believed to be 'pre-Vedic' in orig 3000 BC). The degree of sanctity of these sacred forests varies. In some forests even the dry foliage and the fallen fruits of trees are not touched. In others, the deadwood may be picked up, but never the live trees or their branches. Even the animals and the birds are not disturbed. The garo and khasi tribes of north-eastern india completely prohibit any human interference into their sacred groves. The gond of central india, prohibit the cutting of a tree, but only the fallen branch can be used (jain 1986).

Sacred groves are found all over india in the tribal zones they represent the only surviving examples of climax vegetation. At present there are over 400 groves in maharashtra, (gadgil and vartak 1976) and about the same number in madhya pradesh. There are several in the north- eastern states of india including assam and meghalaya. Many sacred forests exist in rajasthan and gujarat. The andamans, nilgiris and western ghats in the south india also have several such protected forests. The 'mawflong near shillong in meghalaya, and the 'mangaon' and 'ghol in western mountain ranges in the ghats of peninsular india are some prime examples of virgin forests protected and preserved by the aborigines of india (vartak and gadgil 1981).

Such virgin forests are usually located at the origins of forest water springs in the catchment areas of river basins which are potential source of 'hydro-power today. Ironically dams for electricity generation are being built in these areas only to the great disadvantage of the poor tribals who have preserved this natural heritage for centuries. Thousands of tribal have been uprooted to become 'ecological refugees' for dam construction in india. Sardar sarovar and narmada sagar projects of madhya pradesh and gujarat in india are prime examples. This also means that the functional relationship between the forest cover, rainfall, water percolation and soil conservation i.e. the basic variables of the 'hydrological cycles' was known to these aboriginal people since a long time and that must have been another reason why they protected these forests and forest patches by declaring them sacred. These primitive virgin forests of the tribals also preserved. several 'wild varieties' of biologically diverse flora and fauna in their 'native state'. Since many of them are on the extinction list of nature their

survival in these sacred groves is of great ecological significance for the biosphere. Prime example is the prized medicinal plant *Rawolfta serpentina* yielding reserpine' drug for the treatment of high blood pressure and which has disappeared from nature except for these sacred forests preserved by the tribals. These virgin forest patches contribute significantly in the maintenance of biological diversity and ecological balance of the country.

The sacred groves of ancient times have become the 'Biosphere Reserves' of today and are found in several parts of India. The States with larger tribal populations have greater number of biosphere reserves in the form of Wild Life Sanctuaries and National Parks. Madhya Pradesh with the largest tribal population alone has 42, Himachal has 29, Rajasthan has 23, Karnataka 19, Uttar Pradesh 17, Orissa and Gujarat have 16 each, Kerala and Maharashtra 14 each, 12 in Tamil Nadu while the East and the North-Eastern States of India comprising Bihar, Bengal and Assam with greater tribal population have altogether 49 biosphere reserves. Today India has 54 National Parks in about 21003 sq. km. and 372 Wild Life Sanctuaries in about 88649 sq. km. and a major part of these is the legacy of the tribal communities of India. All other sacred groves of tribals should be declared as the 'national sanctuaries' and protected through special legislative measures. of Andaman & Nicobar Islands and the Todas of Tamil Nadu have reverence for coconut trees (*Coccus nucifera*). Several tribes of Bihar, Bengal, U.P. and Orissa have great regards for Mango (*Mangifera indica*) and Imli trees (*Tamarindus indica*) and actually worship them during their weddings (Sinha 1991).

The medico-botanical legacy: contribution to the development of traditional herbal medicine in India

The ancient literature of India and world on medicine suggests that the primitive people of antiquity have been using several kinds of medicinal plants for combating diseases. The ancient Indians used the 'Snake root plant (*Rawolfia serpentina*) about 3000 years ago to treat several diseases from mental disorders to 'insomnia' and 'snake bite. They also used the poppy juice (*Papavar somniferum*) to relieve pain and anxiety. Some knowledge of the ancient Indian medicine and the medicinal herbs has descended through generations and survived through times among the tribal communities of India (Bodding 1925). The circumstances under which these people lived abject poverty, disease and hunger combined with their natural curiosity towards their closest neighbour- the forest in which they lived and

sought its help in mitigating their woes and sorrows must have been an essential factor in preserving the knowledge of plants and their utility to mankind. This wealth of knowledge about the medicinal plants and their healing properties they inherited from their forefathers and also by their own experience after centuries of trial and error. The tribal medicine men in different tribal communities of India give traditional treatment with medicinal herbs for a wide variety of ecological diseases and ailments ranging from Rheumatism, Paralysis, Epilepsy, Dropsy, Leprosy, Jaundice, Diabetes and Malaria to Syphilis, Gonorrhoea, Chronic constipation, Dysentery and Diarrhoea (Sinha 1988). They also treat various skin diseases, womens diseases and

Many of these tribal societies of India have reverence for particular trees also. The Mundas and Santals of Bihar, worship Mahua (*Bassia Latifolia*) and Kadamba (*Anthocephalus cadambe*) trees; the Bhuyias and Gonds of Madhya Pradesh consider Palash (*Butea monosperma*) as sacred; the Bhils and Garassias of Rajasthan have reverence for Khejri trees (*Prosopis cineraria*); the Bagota of Andhra Pradesh, Jarwan. bone fractures. And above all one interesting thing is that they have discovered some kind of a 'herbal oral contraceptive for both male and female to regulate their fertility (Sinha 1989). This is very significant for a country like India where population control is of primary concern for the health authorities. A cheaper and safer 'herbal contraceptive' is the need of the hour. Tewary (1980) reported about the treatment of Insanity, Jaundice, Rabies, Snakebites, Bone fracture and Malaria by the Garo and Khasi Tribes of Meghalaya in India. Vartak, et al. (1981) reported the medicinal plants used by the tribals of Maharashtra for controlling high fever, Rheumatic pains, and Jaundice. K. Hemadri (1984) reported that the folk claims from the tribals of Andhra Pradesh for the treatment of Leucorrhoea, Menorrhagia and Jaundice. Nair et al. (1985) reported on the medico-botany of Andaman and Nicobar tribes and Molla (1985) reported about the traditional treatment of laundice, Rheumatism, Hernia, Gastric Ulcer, Bronchitis and effective use of herbal contraceptives by the Rabha tribes of Bengal. Shah (1985) has reported about ethno medicine of Gujarat tribes. Aminuddin (1987) reported about anti- Malarial plant drugs from the tribal pockets of Orissa.

The plants which are commonly used by all these tribals for preparation of herbal drugs frequently grow in the tribal belts of India. Some important medicinal plants used by them are Sarp Gandha (*Rawolfia serpentina*), Sanai (*Cassia angustifolia*) Asvagandha

(*Withania somnifera*), Satavari (*Asparagus racemosus*), Semal (*Salamalia malabaricum*), Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*), Mulethee (*Glycyrrhiza glabra*), Baibirang (*Embelia ribes*), Nagakesar (*Messua ferra*), Gokhru (*Tribulus terrestris*), Brahami Buti (*Centella asiatica*), Shankpushpi (*Evolvulus alsinoides*), Sanjiwani (*Selaginella bryopteris*), Amaltas (*Cassia fistula*), Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica*), Bahera (*Terminalia bellerica*), Kutki (*Picrorhiza kurroa*), Dhak (*Butea monosperma*), Castor (*Ricinus communis*), Chirchiri (*Achyranthus aspera*), Lajwanti (*Mimosa pudica*), Barahmi (*Bacopa monniera*), Kiwanch (*Mucuna pruriens*), Vidari Kand (*Pueraria tuberosa*), Poppy (*papaver smniferum*) and Gurmar buti (*gymnema sylvestre*) etc.

Significantly several of the above medicinal plants which etc. were being used by the aborigines of India for centuries have found wide acceptance and application in other traditional systems of medicine e.g. Ayurveda, Siddha & Unani medicines and even in the modern medicine. The modern medicine has usurped several of these medicinal plants used by the tribals after chemical investigation revealed some active ingredients of significant biological action in them. The cases of Sarp Gandha (*Rawolfia serpentina*) which yielded 'Reserpine' to reduce high blood pressure, and Morphine from Poppy (*papaver somniferum*) which is a potent analgesic today are worth mentioning. Asvagandha (*Withania somnifera*) has yielded a compound called 'Withanolide D and Withaferin A' from the leaves which have significant 'anti-tumor' activity in vivo against Sarcoma-180 cells in mice. They inhibit RNA Synthesis in them. It also has 'anabolic' action. Gurmar buti (*Gymnema sylvestre*) has a chemical called Gynemic Acid which reduces 'blood sugar. Brahami Buti (*Centella asiatica*) has chemicals with 'anti-leprotic' properties. Kutki (*Picrorhiza Kurroa*) has a chemical with 'hepato-protective' action and lowers blood serum bilirubin in jaundice patients. Dhak (*Butea monosperma*) has 'contraceptive' potentiality and is also 'anti-helminthic'. Giloy (*Tinospora cordifolia*) induces 'indigenous insulin secretion' and 'anti-viral' activities. Sanai (*Cassia angustifolia*) has chemicals called 'Sinnoside A' and 'Sinnoside B' which have strong laxative action and increase peristaltic movement of the intestine. Shankpushpi (*Evolvulus alsinoides*) has potent 'psychedelic' and 'psycholytic' effects. Nagakesar (*Messua ferrae*) has great 'bronchio-dilator' effects. Amaltas (*Cassia fistula*) has been found to be a great 'anti-viral' weapon. More researches will reveal the medical value of several other tribal medicinal plants.

The cultural legacy: Contribution to the modern art and craft and national honour

Since the tribals are descendents of some primitive human civilization, they have inherited a rich cultural heritage from their past ancestors. The traditional folk dance, folk songs, folk instruments, folk art, folk crafts and folk language are some aspects of a unique cultural heritage of these primitive forest people. This has been of considerable economic significance to modern human society.

Several of their traditional skills have taught the modern man the art and technique of utilizing the local natural resources and the forest waste products for useful purposes without harming the environment. In the modern world when the resources are fast depleting there is lot that we can learn from these aboriginal laymen about the new and alternative resources for mankind.

The knowledge of the use of canes, bamboos and plant fibres for making modern furniture, ropes, mats and baskets; use of animal hides and skins for making shoes, purses, wallets and other leather articles; the use of vegetable dyes for dyeing and coloring industries, all must have come from the cultural practices of these primitive men. Moreover, the knowledge of the use of other valuable material like vegetable oils, honey, gums, resins, waxes and silk producing worms also came from the tribals who utilize these natural products of forest for their livelihood. The tribals are hardy people and have inherited a higher level of power of 'endurance'. They have learnt to cope with difficult situations in the hills and forest. Their descendents today are contributing greatly in the nation's defence build up, sports and athletics. Tribal's from Bihar and North East of India occupy important positions in the national hockey and football teams. Tribals from Rajasthan represented India in world archery. They have earned a great honour and prestige for the country in several national and international events.

Concluding

The tribals a vanishing relic of the primitive human societies and because the forest cover and the hills from where these people originated and brought the wealth o medico-botancial and agro-botancial knowledge and the cultural and ecological heritage, are fast disappearing under the impact of industrialization and urbanization of modern human civilization, these tribals are also becoming acculturated and losing their knowledge and

experience (Schultes 1968). Hence, at what really concerns the human ecologists and anthropologists today is how to salvage some of those valuable legacies of the tribals before they disappear forever with the culture that gave them birth.

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